
INDUCTION SERVICES AND TEACHERS' PRODUCTIVITY IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

¹Onyeka, R. O., ²Asiyai, R. I., and ³Anho, J. E.

^{1,2&3}Department of Educational Management and Foundations,
Delta State University Abraka

ABSTRACT

This study examined induction services and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. Two research questions and hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population for the study comprised 15,225 educators in public secondary schools in Delta State, consisting of 14,745 teachers and 479 principals. A total of 52 principals and 418 teachers from 52 public secondary schools (26 urban and 26 rural) were sampled using a stratified sampling technique. The instruments used for data collection were the Induction Services Questionnaire (ISQ) and Teachers' Job Productivity Questionnaire (TJPQ). The face and content validity of the instruments were established through expert judgment. The reliability of the instruments was tested using the Cronbach Alpha method to determine internal consistency. Reliability indices of 0.82 and 0.83 were obtained for the ISQ and TJPQ, respectively, indicating strong internal consistency. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, as well as independent sample t-tests at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the induction services available to teachers in urban and rural schools and induction services do not have a significant influence on teachers' job productivity. This suggests that teachers in urban schools may benefit from more structured, comprehensive, and resource-rich induction programmes compared to their rural counterparts. It was recommended, among other things, that the authorities and educational stakeholders implement a standardized induction programme across all public secondary schools in Delta State to ensure that both urban and rural teachers receive thorough training and support.

Keywords: Induction Services, Teachers' Job Productivity, Public Secondary Schools, Urban-Rural Disparities

INTRODUCTION

A teacher is a trained professional responsible for facilitating learning by guiding, instructing, and supporting students to acquire knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values. Teachers are the backbone of any educational system; they translate curriculum objectives into practical learning experiences and play a central role in shaping the intellectual, moral, and social development of learners. The effectiveness of an educational system largely depends on the productivity of its teachers, making them indispensable to national development. Teachers' job productivity refers to the degree to which teachers effectively and efficiently carry out their instructional and non-instructional duties to achieve desirable educational outcomes. It encompasses the ability of teachers to plan and deliver lessons, manage classrooms, assess student performance, engage in continuous professional development, and contribute to the overall goals of the school. According to Obi (2023), teachers' productivity is measured by the extent to which the teacher achieves instructional objectives, fosters positive student behavior, and contributes to students' academic performance. Similarly, Adeniji (2022) posits that a productive teacher is one who demonstrates competence in subject matter delivery, classroom control, and the use of varied teaching strategies to meet the needs of diverse learners. One key factor that may impact teacher job productivity is the availability and quality of induction services provided to newly employed teachers. Induction services are systematic and structured support programmes designed to ease teachers' transition into the teaching profession by equipping them with the necessary skills, knowledge, and professional orientation (Ingersoll & Strong, 2021). These services often include mentoring, workshops, collaborative planning, classroom observation, and feedback mechanisms that help new teachers navigate instructional responsibilities and school culture.

Klein and Weaver (2000) described an induction programme as a type of employee training aimed at familiarizing new hires with their job roles and responsibilities, co-workers and organizations. Well-designed induction programmes provide a positive return for the employer in various ways, such as increased employee productivity, loyalty, retention and overall contribution to the organization. This process helps new employees acclimate to the organization culture, understand their roles and responsibilities and develop the skills necessary for success (Outlaw, 2018). Corroborating the above, Hattie (2016) maintained that every school must develop programmes that will support the professional development of teachers and one of such programmes is induction. According to Hattie, the professional development of teachers through induction is a lifelong process that starts at initial teacher education and ends at retirement. Hattie further emphasized that any induction system should address new teachers' needs by providing three fundamental types of support: personal, social and professional.

Yeye (2020) maintained that starting work in a new school can be just as overwhelming for new teachers as it is for new students. The new things they need to learn range from information systems to human relation and curriculum. Developing an effective teacher, induction programme can ease the transition for new teachers, giving them the time, support and relationships they need to thrive. In the same vein, Grants (2016) admitted that once new teachers are employed they have to be told about the schools' rules and regulations, the procedure for academic activities such as sessional tests, assignments seminar presentations, summer training, semester examinations and the subject to be taught. A new employee enters the organization as a stranger to his/her colleagues, role and the workplace itself, often leading to initial anxiety. In some cases, this anxiety may even result in unexpected resignations. It culminates at times to surprise resignation by the new employee.

Hence arrangements need to be made to make the integration of fresh recruits entering into the organization as smooth as possible to help them to be free of anxiety.

Induction of educators specifically can simply be seen as support programmes especially for beginning to teachers. Martinez (2020) sees induction as a critical phase in a continuum of professional development for both new and old teachers. Martinez further concluded that an introductory training involves familiarization with both the profession and the organization, providing personal and professional support, along with chances to enhance the knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for successful teaching. Induction is imperative in helping to produce teachers that remain in the profession. Induction is the collection of programmes involving orientation, support and guidance for beginning teachers. Ashton and Webb (2016), defined induction as a programme for beginning teachers in an initial and essential step in the continuum of professional development to help early career teachers overcome the obstacles and challenges of the early years of teaching and to reduce the risk of attrition, improve classroom teaching and learning dynamics. It improves teachers' retention in the early years of a career. Induction also improves teachers' knowledge and students' achievements. Nkedishu and Nwaorgu (2022) noted that school culture significantly influences how new teachers respond to induction services and subsequently commit to their professional responsibilities, demonstrating the interconnection between institutional environment and teacher productivity

Gill (2010) defines the induction of new educators as a series of processes designed to enhance the experiences of beginning teachers, helping them acquire the necessary skills to succeed in their assigned teaching roles. To some extent, induction resembles the professional development programmes that more experienced teachers undergo. However, the methods and processes of induction are specifically focused on the fundamental principles of teaching. The overall concept of induction has been to anticipate the issues a new teacher will be faced with during the first and second years of teaching and then providing the new teacher with the right information and knowledge to be successful in the classroom and the teaching environment in general. The more successful a beginning teacher and the quicker they experience success, the greater they will remain in the teaching profession. The establishment of mentorship relationships during teacher induction correlates with increased productivity metrics, reflecting findings about professional development approaches unique to Nigeria's educational context (Nkedishu & Osakwe, 2017).

Induction is a broad term refers to the support systems established to help educators adjust to a new workplace culture. It extends beyond understanding students, classes and the curriculum; it also includes information about the systems and processes that govern the workplace, as well as the school's norms, all of which are essential for them to settle in and feel self-assured. Induction is a process of introducing new employees to the organization in other words, it serves as a well-orchestrated event aimed at socializing the new entrant with the people and the work environment in a particular organization (Yeye, 2020). According to Fluckiger, McGlamery and Edick (2016), induction is the process of welcoming and orienting new employees when they first join a company, providing them with the essential information they need to settle in quickly and comfortably and begin their work. It is a method through which a new employee is integrated into the new environment, familiarized with the organization's practices, policies and goals. It is a technique by which a new employee is rehabilitated into the changed surroundings and introduced to the practices, policies and purposes of the organization. Induction is therefore the process of welcoming, indoctrinating and socializing a new employee to his/her job and organization.

The induction of secondary school teachers and teachers in its entirety, especially new ones remain very fundamental and key to improving their productive performance of both the new teachers and the school system at large. Hence, the induction of newly appointed teachers has a whole lot of benefits. Camp and Heath (2018) observed that a well-organized induction scheme provides the ensuing advantages for the newcomers and the organization; reduces anxiety, nervousness, absenteeism, and employee turnover. It also helps minimize the cultural shock new employees may face when joining a new organization. Through effective induction, new employees are better integrated into the organization, fostering a strong sense of belonging. Moreover, induction brings both newcomers and existing employees together, strengthening teamwork. According to Kelchtermans and Ballet (2017), the introduction of induction programmes play a role in the development of a learning culture within the school, such a learning culture focuses not only on supporting the learning of beginning teachers, but also on the learning of all teaching personnel in the school. The mentor plays a key role in fostering an environment where the input of beginning teachers is valued and taken seriously, while also nurturing a culture of learning throughout the school. Kelchtermans and Ballet maintained that induction programmes can serve multiple purposes, including reducing teacher turnover, enhancing the quality of beginning teachers, offering support in professional, social, and emotional aspects, strengthening the learning culture within schools and providing feedback to teacher education institutions. Well-structured induction programmes aim to address these objectives in a cohesive manner.

Mangione, Patrizia and Pettenati (2018) indicated that if teachers have support and training they are much more likely to remain in the job which ultimately leads to a rise in the teacher retention rates. First-year teachers are typically assigned to the same tasks, in and out of the classroom, as a seasoned educator. Quality programmes are crucial for first-year teachers, and research has shown that new teachers who participate in such programmes are almost twice as likely to remain in the job compared to those who do not. In the opinion of Anorld (2019) a well-planned induction process for the newly employed, introduces them to all these procedural details and offers them hand-on experience in using them. It prevents the employee from having to be anxious about how to submit a time card when he is trying to be productive at his new job. He further posited that an employee who is hired into a new position with no orientation can feel overwhelmed and will not have the understanding necessary to do the job, this happens because he is not properly trained, errors may show up that this employee may be blamed for and that can cause employee's turnover. Having a thorough employee orientation programme enables employees to gain a clear understanding of their roles. It reduces the possibility that a new employee will leave the organization because he feels he cannot withstand the pressure of being newly employed. Several scholars have over time expressed their dissatisfaction towards the mentorship for new teachers in public secondary schools in Nigeria. For instance, Asuquo (2015) maintained that the induction of newly employed teachers in public secondary schools in Nigeria is very poor, as they are rarely given any form of formal induction. Asuquo added that newly employed teachers in government schools are not sufficiently guided, assisted and educated about their job as often seen in other non-educational organizations.

The availability and quality of induction services for teachers often vary significantly based on school location, particularly between urban and rural settings. In urban schools, induction programmes tend to be more structured, well-resourced, and systematically implemented due to better access to educational infrastructure, experienced mentors, and administrative support (Afolabi, 2013). Conversely, teachers in rural schools may experience limited or poorly coordinated induction services, often due to inadequate funding, shortage of

qualified personnel, and logistical challenges (Oyetunde & Adedokun, 2014). These disparities can lead to unequal professional development opportunities for teachers, thereby affecting their job performance and long-term productivity. Teachers in urban schools may benefit from regular workshops, peer collaboration, and instructional coaching, while those in remote areas may lack mentorship and professional guidance during the critical early years of their career. Consequently, school location becomes a determining factor in the extent to which induction services can enhance teacher effectiveness and retention.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A whole lot of public schools within this study area lack adequate and well-organized induction programmes in place with the aim of assisting new teachers' rapid adjustment, integration, compatibility and performance. Often, new teachers are only given orientation by way of introducing the teachers to old teachers and students at the assembly ground or taking them round the various classrooms for introduction to the students. Mere introduction of the newly employed teachers to colleagues and students is not enough to equip the teachers with all the necessary information and knowledge needed for optimum performance and also quick adjustment integration and compatibility of their professional environment. Hence they are often left alone to struggle in their roles and learn to cope with the job. Such non-supportive atmosphere and tendency is very likely to result in anxiety, frustration, depression, stress, under performance and eventually voluntary retirement, attrition and brain drain in the teaching profession. Asuquo (2015) observed that induction in public secondary schools in Nigeria is very poor as new teachers are seldom given any form of formal induction. Thus, it is in realization of the above problem that this study focused on the need to induct new teachers for improved job performance in Delta State public secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. Are there differences in the induction services available to teachers in urban and rural public secondary schools in Delta State?
2. To what extent do induction services influence teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the induction services available to teachers in urban and rural public secondary schools in Delta State.
2. There is no significant difference between urban and rural respondents on the impact of induction services on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State.

METHODOLOGY

An ex-post facto design, incorporating both descriptive and correlational approaches, was used in this study. The population for the study comprised 15,225 educators in public secondary schools in Delta State, consisting of 14,745 teachers and 479 principals. A total of 52 principals and 418 teachers from 52 public secondary schools (26 urban and 26 rural) were sampled using a stratified sampling technique. The data collection instruments employed were the Induction Services Questionnaire (ISQ) and the Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ), which were used to gather information from the respondents. Face and

content validity were established through expert judgment. The reliability of the instruments was tested using the Cronbach Alpha method, yielding reliability indices of 0.82 and 0.83 for the ISQ and TPQ, respectively, indicating strong internal consistency. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation, and coefficient of determination. Hypotheses were tested using independent sample t-tests and Pearson Product Moment Correlation at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: Are there differences in the induction services available to teachers in urban and rural public secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean scores on Differences in the Induction Services Available to Teachers in Urban and Rural Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

S/N	Available Induction services	Urban School =(N=208) Teachers			Rural Schools(N=210)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Orientation workshops on school policies	3.25	0.82	Accepted	3.15	0.89	Accepted
2.	Mentoring programmes with experienced teachers.	2.9	0.75	Accepted	2.7	0.78	Accepted
3.	Provision of detailed teacher handbooks.	3.3	0.98	Accepted	3.1	0.97	Accepted
4.	Regular classroom observations	2.8	0.33	Accepted	2.6	0.35	Accepted
5.	Collaborative planning sessions with colleagues.	3.15	0.85	Accepted	3.25	0.86	Accepted
6.	Training on teaching methodologies.	3.45	0.9	Accepted	3.25	0.91	Accepted
7.	Introduction to the school's culture.	3.1	0.84	Accepted	3.00	0.83	Accepted
8.	Access to online resources.	2.95	0.88	Accepted	2.55	0.86	Accepted
9.	Meetings with school administrators for guidance.	3.2	0.7	Accepted	3.1	0.78	Accepted
10.	Peer feedback sessions.	2.75	0.85	Accepted	2.65	0.88	Accepted
	Grand mean	3.08	0.79		2.93	0.81	Accepted

Bench mark mean=2.50

Table 1 clearly highlights the mean scores of induction services available to teachers in urban and rural public secondary schools in Delta State. For urban schools, items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 have mean scores of 3.25, 2.90, 3.30, 2.80, 3.15, 3.45, 3.10, 2.95, 3.20, and 2.75 respectively, all of which are above the benchmark mean of 2.50. This indicates that these induction services are accepted as being available in urban schools. Similarly, in rural schools, items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 have mean scores of 3.15, 2.70, 3.10, 2.60, 3.25, 3.25, 3.00, 2.55, 3.10, and 2.65 respectively, also above the benchmark mean of 2.50. This suggests that the same induction services are available in rural schools, though at slightly lower levels in most cases. It was therefore concluded that induction services such as orientation workshops, mentoring programmes, provision of teacher handbooks, classroom observations, collaborative planning, training on teaching methodologies, introduction to

school culture, access to online resources, administrative guidance, and peer feedback sessions are available in both urban and rural public secondary schools in Delta State. However, teachers in urban schools appear to benefit more from structured and resource-enriched induction programmes, particularly in access to online resources, teacher mentoring, and professional training opportunities, when compared to their rural counterparts.

Research Question 2: To what extent do induction services influence teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 2: Pearson correlation and coefficient of determination of the extent do induction services influence teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State

Variable	N	X	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Remark
Induction service	416	2.65	.79	.039	.002	0.2	Marginal positive influence
Teachers' productivity	52	3.37	.68				

Table 2 presents the Pearson correlation analysis between induction services and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State. The result shows a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of .039, indicating a very weak positive relationship between the two variables. The coefficient of determination (r²) is .002, which translates to 0.2% of the variance in teachers' job productivity being explained by induction services. It can therefore be concluded that induction services have a marginal positive influence on teachers' job productivity

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the induction services available to teachers in urban and rural public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 3: Difference Between Urban and Rural Respondents on Induction Exposure

School Location	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	t-crit.	Decision
Urban teachers	208	3.08	.87	416	3.77	±1.96	Significant
Rural teachers	210	2.93	.81				

A t-test was conducted to determine if there was a statistically significant difference differences in the induction services available to teachers in urban and rural public secondary schools in Delta State. The results showed a t-value of 3.77 with 416 degrees of freedom (df). The t-critical value was ±1.96, which is less than the t-calculated value of 3.77 at 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that there was a statistically significant difference differences in the induction services available to teachers in urban and rural public secondary schools in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2: Induction services have no significant influence on teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 4: Pearson correlation Analysis of the influence induction services ON teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State

		Teachers' Induction	Teachers' Productivity
Teachers' Induction	Pearson Correlation	1	.039
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.711
	N	418	52
Teachers' Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.039	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.711	
	N	52	52

Table 4 shows a Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the influence induction services on teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State ($r = 0.039$, $p = 0.711$). This is determined by comparing the p-value to the alpha level. The p-value is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This indicates that there is no the null hypothesis, which states that induction services do not significantly influence teachers' job productivity.

DISCUSSION

Firstly, the study found that there is a statistically significant difference in the induction services available to teachers in urban and rural schools. Teachers in urban areas reported higher mean scores across several induction activities, such as orientation workshops, mentoring programmes, access to online resources, and training on teaching methodologies. These services were more structured and resource-rich compared to what was available to their rural counterparts. This disparity suggests that urban schools are better positioned to provide comprehensive support for newly recruited teachers, likely due to better infrastructure, access to technology, and stronger administrative support. The implication is that teachers in rural schools may not be receiving the same level of professional support during the early stages of their careers, which could impact their effectiveness and overall job satisfaction. Therefore, addressing these gaps in the provision of induction services is crucial for promoting equity and improving teacher development across the state. This finding concurs with the discoveries of Osakwe (2023) whose study finds that the challenges of management of teachers in urban and rural secondary schools in Delta state include the following; lack of motivation of teachers, overcrowded classrooms, relegation of the teaching career, nonpayment of allowances, dilapidated school facilities, poor work environment, inadequate supervision, inadequate school facilities, lack of capacity building, inadequate finance, frequent change in educational policies, inadequate teachers, corruption, unqualified teachers, bias in employment process and lack of ICT facilities. It highlighted the universal need for effective induction and continuous professional development across all schools. A study by Chime (2024) found that school location significantly influences teacher job commitment, with urban teachers displaying higher levels of commitment compared to their counterparts in rural areas. This suggests that induction and mentorship mechanisms may be more robust in urban settings, contributing to greater teacher engagement. Futhermore, Okoi, Ameh, and Omini (2024) revealed significant differences in the allocationof educational resources across urban and rural schools. Urban schools were better equipped with basic amenities and had a more favorable allocation of teachers, which can enhance the effectiveness of induction programmes. On the other hand, rural schools often faced shortages in both resources and qualified personnel, hindering comprehensive induction processes. A study by Owede (2019) highlighted an imbalance in teacher distribution favoring urban schools. Aspects such as school location, availability of facilities, and teachers' marital status influenced postings, leading to a concentration of educators in urban

areas. This imbalance suggests that rural teachers may have less access to well-organized induction programmes and ongoing professional development opportunities. Disparities in the induction and professional development opportunities available to teachers in urban versus rural public secondary schools in Delta state can impact teacher commitment, resource availability and overall educational quality.

Secondly, the study showed that induction services do not have a significant influence on teachers' job productivity. The Pearson correlation coefficient indicated only a weak positive relationship between induction services and job productivity, which was not statistically significant. This finding suggests that, although induction services are generally available, they may not be effectively designed or implemented to influence measurable outcomes in teachers' performance. It is possible that these programmes are too generic, short-term, or disconnected from the actual challenges teachers face in the classroom. Additionally, other factors such as ongoing professional development, school leadership, motivation, and working conditions might play a more substantial role in shaping teachers' productivity. This finding supports earlier work by Imoke and Ezeani (2018) who found that the effectiveness of induction programmes depends on how systematically they are planned, delivered, and integrated into the broader teacher development framework. This finding conforms to the findings of Anho (2022) who found that professional growth and induction initiatives are crucial in enhancing students' performance in external examinations. The research emphasized that teachers who undergo systematic induction have greater capacity to address students' academic needs, leading to improved outcomes. Also, a study by Akiri (2013) found that effective educators, typically those who have undergone comprehensive induction programmes, tend to produce better-performing students.

CONCLUSION

This study examined induction services and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Delta State. The findings revealed a significant difference in the induction services provided to teachers in urban and rural areas, with urban schools offering more comprehensive and better-structured induction programmes. This indicates a disparity in support structures for teachers based on school location, which may contribute to unequal professional experiences and opportunities for teacher development. However, despite the presence of induction services, the study found that these services do not significantly influence teachers' job productivity. The weak, non-significant correlation suggests that while induction programmes exist, they may not be effectively tailored to address the practical needs of teachers or impact their job performance meaningfully. Based on these findings, it is concluded that for induction services to be more impactful, there is a need for equitable distribution, improvement in quality, and better alignment with teachers' professional challenges. Strengthening the design, delivery, and monitoring of induction programmes—especially in rural schools—can enhance their effectiveness and potentially lead to improved teacher productivity across Delta State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Delta State Ministry of Secondary Education should take proactive steps to design and implement a standardized induction programme for all public secondary schools across the state. Such a programme should be uniformly adopted in both urban and rural schools to ensure that every teacher receives thorough training and consistent professional support, regardless of location.

2. Post-Primary Education Board (PPEB) should monitor and evaluate the implementation of induction programmes in schools to ensure they contribute meaningfully to teachers' job performance and address specific professional needs.

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